

ELIXIR Commissioned Service ELIXIR Training Platform 24-26, Work Package 3 - Consolidating ELIXIR Training standards and best practices for Open science and Open education

D3.2 Version 1: Guidelines on standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS. Guidelines on how to integrate the LP process within the whole Training Lifecycle framework. Production of webpage content on LP to be shown on Training SPLASH

Tier: TECHNOLOGY

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the first version of guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), and supporting content for the ELIXIR Learning Paths (LPs) initiative, developed as part of Work Package 3 (WP3 – Activity 1) under the ELIXIR Training Platform Work Plan (2024–2026). The main objective is to formalise a shared, sustainable process for the creation and maintenance of LPs in TeSS, while integrating them coherently into the broader ELIXIR Training Lifecycle (TLC) framework.

The problem addressed stems from the growing relevance of LPs as a way to organise training around thematic areas. Despite some successful pilots, the absence of shared governance structures and operational procedures limited consistency, reuse, and long-term sustainability. This deliverable responds to that gap by providing coordinated guidance and standardisation.

It includes three core components:

- (1) an SOP defining roles, responsibilities, and workflows for the LP Editorial Board;
- (2) a document outlining how LPs align with the five TLC stages (Plan, Design, Develop, Deliver, Evaluate), including an updated visual of the LP Protocol;
- (3) dedicated content for the Training SPLASH website, increasing visibility and offering testimonials from both internal and external users.

Currently, no alternative governance frameworks for LPs exist within ELIXIR. Therefore, this SOP marks the first coordinated step in standardising LP-related activities. The conclusions point to increased coherence, quality, and recognition of LPs, with future iterations (D3.2 v2 and v3) planned to refine the approach based on implementation feedback and further community engagement.

Document info

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

LP	Learning Path
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TLC	Training Life Cycle
WP ₃	Work Package 3

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Outcomes and expected impact

This deliverable represents a foundational step in formalising ELIXIR's approach to LPs, with the aim of supporting structured, scalable, and high-quality training across the ELIXIR ecosystem and beyond. It directly contributes to the objectives of WP₃ – Activity 1 by aligning LPs with the ELIXIR TLC framework, establishing clear governance and quality standards for their development and maintenance. Additionally, it improves the visibility and accessibility of all related documentation and outcomes via the SPLASH portal, featuring case studies and testimonials that serve as practical examples to inform and inspire future implementations.

Outcomes:

- The [SOP for the Editorial Board for the Development and Maintenance of ELIXIR Learning Paths in TeSS \(v1\)](#)¹, defining roles, responsibilities, and workflows for the Editorial Boards (General and LP-Specific Editorial Board), ensuring that ELIXIR Learning Paths hosted in TeSS are well-governed, high-quality, and regularly maintained. The document is the result of a thorough and collaborative process, developed through extensive consultation and alignment with all relevant stakeholders, including the TeSS team, the Learning Paths Focus Group, and ELIXIR Training Coordinators. This SOP promotes fair recognition of contributors and encourages collaborative development across the ELIXIR ecosystem.
- The [guidance document entitled Integrating Learning Paths into the Training Life Cycle](#)², which identifies key touchpoints where LPs can be meaningfully integrated within the five TLC stages (Plan, Design, Develop, Deliver, Evaluate). The document promotes a cohesive approach to using the LP Protocol (the main resource developed to design LPs) as a tool throughout the cycle. This output is the result of discussions that were revised and consolidated. It was subsequently shared and validated during the Workshop to consolidate the key components of TLC [2024-11-22 Training Life Cycle Review Workshop Agenda](#)
- [An enriched Learning Paths page on the SPLASH website](#), providing links to core guidance, relevant activities, and resources. It also includes selected testimonials from both internal ELIXIR initiatives and external collaborations (EOSC₄Cancer, BSC - Barcelona Supercomputing Center), demonstrating the growing recognition of LPs as a valuable instrument for structuring training across different scientific domains.

Expected impact:

- Improved adoption and coherence of LPs across ELIXIR ecosystem, through clear guidelines and centralised governance structures.
- Better alignment between training initiatives and ELIXIR's strategic objectives, by embedding LPs within the TLC framework and operationalising their integration through shared protocols.
- Increased visibility and usability of LPs via the SPLASH platform, encouraging reuse and adoption by the broader research training community.
- Recognition and sustainability of LPs as a collaborative training mechanism, ensuring that contributions are acknowledged and learning content remains relevant over time.

These outcomes set the stage for the subsequent versions of the deliverable, which will further refine and complete the documentation.

¹[SOP for the Editorial Board for the Development and Maintenance of ELIXIR Learning Paths in TeSS \(v1\)](#)

²[Integrating Learning Paths into the Training Life Cycle \(v1\)](#)

Dissemination Plans

The deliverable and its associated documents are intended for public dissemination and will be made openly available through the following channels:

[Training SPLASH website](#): dedicated sections have been created, and will continue to be expanded, on the SPLASH website to present the LP project. These sections include links to the SOP, guidelines, related activities, supporting resources, and testimonials from both internal and external collaborators. Together, they provide context and concrete use cases that demonstrate real-world impact, ensuring that training providers and other stakeholders can easily access, consult, and adopt the guidance provided.

[TeSS infrastructure](#): LPs developed and maintained in accordance with the Editorial Board SOP will be made visible and accessible through the TeSS platform, serving as concrete applications of the LP framework and enhancing visibility within the wider training ecosystem.

[GitHub - LP Handbook](#): the documentation developed as part of this deliverable will also be made available via a dedicated repository on ELIXIR's GitHub, a Handbook focused on LPs developed and managed under the Learning Paths Focus Group. This is a resource we plan to develop further in upcoming Training Platform Work Programmes.

Presentations and webinars: dissemination of the SOP, TLC integration document, and SPLASH LP webpage will be supported through targeted presentations at ELIXIR Training-related meetings (e.g. Training Coordinator calls, Focus Group meetings, and AHM sessions), as well as through dedicated workshops open to the ELIXIR Communities.

Future updates (D3.2 v2 and v3) will build upon this initial release and continue to be disseminated via the same open access channels.

Additional dissemination routes may be explored and expanded under the next ELIXIR Training Platform Programme (2027–2028), including future publications and organisation of thematic training events to ensure sustained awareness and uptake of the framework presented in this deliverable.